

Rac-3n

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-78-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	24	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 78 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/26/2022 9:55:10 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/5/2022 9:21:03 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.779	6779380	50.30	298984
2	14.908	6698344	49.70	249534

Asy-3n (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-78-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	42	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 79 asy
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	1/26/2022 10:17:00 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/5/2022 9:19:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.766	22203709	94.52	974707
2	14.897	1288013	5.48	50106